

Impact of Teachers' Attitude towards Profession on Students' Academic Achievement at Secondary School Level

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 16, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Professional Attitude, Secondary Schools, Teacher Profession & Students' Academic Achievement</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5706025</p>	<p><i>This research paper is descriptive-correlation study. The study was impact of teacher attitude towards profession on student's academic achievement at secondary school level. The method was used quantitative and the population of the study was 148 boy's school, 1649 male teachers and 37324 boys' students at secondary school at district Peshawar and Charsadda. The sample technique was used cluster and 600 were male teacher and 400 boy's students were selected in both districts. Scale developed by Renthlei and Malsawmi (2015), Teacher Attitude towards profession which was used for the study. It contains 22 items and uses Likert scale questionnaire which were including 1 to 5 ranges. Annual examination of class X result BISEP (Boards of Intermediate & Secondary Education Peshawar) was the average score of the student's academic achievement. Thousand (1000) questionnaires were personally distributed to respondent and collect the relevant source from the mind of the respondents (teachers, students). Different statistical tools were used for analysis that was one sample t-test, Pearson correlation and regression for testing hypothesis. It was found that teacher attitude towards profession was positive contributive towards students academic achievement. It was also found that teacher attitude profession and student academic achievement was contributive positively towards each others. As a whole teacher attitude towards profession was significant predictor of students' academic achievement. It was concluded that the overall research paper teacher attitude towards profession on students' academic achievement was statistically significant.</i></p>

Introduction

Education has an important place in the development and strengthening of a society and is closely related to its social and economical development. It can be argued that the quality of education in a country depends on its teachers. Teacher is a role model representing specific attitude and self-compassion that leads to their credibility and success in the profession. It is generally observed that some teachers perform well while others are less effective in classroom. Teachers impact the educational, economic, and social lives of their students, and the demands of society can be met by creating teachers who have a positive attitude, are self-compassionate and credible based on a body of theoretical and practical knowledge. Such teachers would then be able to improve the academic achievement of students.

Reddy (2017), Attitude reflects the experiences of teachers in the past and in the present and are expressed through behavior. Teachers' attitude is a consistent predisposition towards their environment. It is suggested that teacher's attitude influences their actions which are interpreted by students through their credibility and affects student achievement.

The literature review is developed the central themes regarding teacher attitude towards profession and its effect on students' academic achievement. The above review provided for better understanding of the government schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan.

Teacher's belief, expectation how they impact on students' academic achievement is important. Literature examines teachers' potential and perceptions of students and effect on their learning outcome (Renthlei and Malsawmi 2015).

Education plays an important role in the society. It cans assurance achievement in different fields of life. Trained peoples of any countries are dependent upon the civilized societies have recognized the importance of education.

Education plays an important role as it lays the foundation for the further education of students at secondary school. If Secondary education is better given to students, then they can better challenges of life. Administration is trying to recognize low performing schools. Teachers need to improve their skills and qualification for better understanding students' academic achievement. School and teachers to align curriculum

and teaching methods it is a great urge with focus on objective standards (Issan, Al-Nabhani, Kazem, and Al-Ani 2011).

The employees in any organization, ' attitude to his profession is significant for achievement. Those employees who have skill, experience and qualification they are known as professional person regarding his profession. Every profession has some specific attitudes based on their thinking towards their job. According to Ahmad & Sahak (2009), person's attitude is reliable tendency towards objects in their atmosphere in a positive/negative technique.

Attitude is composed of a personal person experiences in the present and past reflected performance. Teacher's attitudes towards profession are articulated their actions which are related to student academic achievement. Professional attitude is associated with behavior and a constructive relation between students and teachers, it bring a positive school environment for better student academic achievement (Maliki 2013).

Bhargava & Pathy (2014), attitude is a situation of motivation, through experience and ordered, an individual's response to different situation and objects. Feeling, dispositions and beliefs, are features of attitude. Renthlei and Malsawmi (2015) Attitude is a predisposition to organize object, events and react to them with some reliability. It is not directly visible and is conditional from the evaluative responses of people.

Barros & Elia (2017), attitude involves intellectual preparation relating to postures, actions, and determines what people think, do, hear and see. Peoples' general propensity to events, person, respond to institutions and might be negative i.e., prejudice or positive i.e. values.

According to Shah (2002) Teacher training skill improve teacher attitudes towards teaching profession which effect on students 'academic achievement. Attitudes, practices and beliefs are essential for the improvement of educational processes. According to Khamari and Guru (2013, p.50) summarized the major characteristics of attitude that as, the range of attitude in not limited, attitudes form the roots for behavior, attitude can be both covert and overt, attitudes vary in direction, intensity, and strength, attitudes of individuals are integrated in an organized manner, attitudes are acquired and differ from culture to culture and attitudes are generally consistent and lasting but can be modified.

Vaughn (2012, p.9), some research scholars state that dispositions may be characterized as natural and absolute traits to growth and development. The dispositions are natural and absolute implies a set of personality and that all students will get benefit from teachers possessing those characteristics. Teacher education influences their dispositions on the grounds that people avoid activities and atmosphere that increase their manageable potential and activities. Soibamcha and Pandey (2016), the teacher learned their attitude through life experiences, person situation, objects and make people behave in characteristics towards their profession. Attitudes are basically organized traits of a personality and a product of life experiences.

Maliki (2013), attitudes affect behavior and create a precise value system that impact all traits of social behavior. According to Ahmadi (2015, p.171) attitudes provide a structure for understanding the social atmosphere through its various components. Teacher performance highly depend on teacher-student interactions that how teachers evaluate and examined their students. According to Herrera (2010) teacher's attitudes can be examined by his command over his subject, confident, self awareness and approach to the school atmosphere.

Hartlep and Mc Cubbins (2013, p.6) teacher attitudes and thinking are connected to teacher effective teaching. So, understanding of teacher attitudes is very important in relation to teacher effective teaching and student learning out come. The modern notion for teacher has gone beyond observing, role of management, evaluating, counseling and teaching subjects to a class. The teacher plays an important role regarding the foundation of future generation and continuation of a society.

Quality of teacher teaching depends on teachers attitudes towards their profession. Therefore it is very important to have teacher's attitudes towards their profession. A professional attitude represents the commitment to profession (Shaheen, 2014). Attitude towards profession determines teachers' willingness to develop as a professional. Teachers with a positive attitude towards teaching profession facilitate learning through their commitment and skill. Teachers' attitude towards profession influences their job commitment and students' performance (Wanderi, 2015). Ye, R. (2000) found positive attitude of teachers towards teaching in secondary schools. He argued it important that teachers should be sufficiently remunerated, equipped and prepared to teach in secondary schools. It is argued that teachers' attitudes towards profession is related to their instructional behavior and affects student personality, life experiences, and achievement.

1.2. Statement of the problem

The main purpose of the study was impact of teacher attitude towards profession on students' academic achievement. Teacher attitudes affect teacher behaviors, teacher personality, teacher teaching skills and subject knowledge. Education is meant a tool of socio-economic growth and development. We cannot imagine sound school environment without updated education system. For achieving better outcome, teacher sound attitude is important.

Education system in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa faces diverse challenges like-wise learning environment, poor sanitation, in experienced teachers, well freshened buildings, over populated classrooms, and lack of parent's interaction with school administration.

There is lack of specific information regarding the impacts of teacher attitude towards profession on student academic achievement at Secondary schools in district Peshawar and Charsadda Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Furthermore the review literature clearly depicts relation between teacher attitude and student outcome. The study proposed to add to the research regarding teacher attitude towards profession and student academic achievement.

1.3. Objectives

1. To explore the attitude of teachers of secondary schools in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa the Province of Pakistan
2. To determine whether the teachers' attitude is a predictor of student academic achievement.

1.4. Hypotheses

- H₀. There is no impact on teachers' attitude towards profession students and students' academic achievement.
 H₀. Teachers' attitude is not a significant predictor of student academic achievement.

1.5. Significance of the study

Education experts have shown great interest in determining teacher attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors that increase academic achievement of students. Teacher attitude towards their profession and student academic achievement has played an important role in improving the school environment at district, provincial, and national level.

It is pertinent to mention here that this study has an important role in extending knowledge of teacher attitude towards his profession and student academic achievement. This study also help the principals and teachers to know their attitude towards profession and throw light on how to improve the environment for better student academic achievement. This research study also focused on different dimensions of teachers' attitudes towards their profession that can improve student academic achievement.

This research study is also important for bringing awareness among the staff community and other public and private education sectors about the significance of positive teacher attitude towards their profession and its impact on students' academic achievement.

3.0 Methods and Procedure

The method of the study was descriptive correlation and quantitative research design was used for collection of data. Quantitative research collects numerical data and then analyzed through statistical procedures. The study was conducted in Boys Govt. High secondary schools in District Peshawar & Charsadda. SST Teachers and class X students were requested to complete a survey instrument.

3.1 Population and Sample

The population of this study was male SSTs teachers and boys students at secondary school level in district Peshawar and district charsadda. There were 148 boy's schools, 1649 male SSTs teachers and 37324 boys' students in class X. A total of 600 SSTs male teachers and 400 boys students were selected from a population. Sample random cluster sampling technique was used. Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table was used for selection of the sampling. Therefore, 600 male teachers and 400 boys' students were taken as sample of the study.

3.2 Data collection Instrument

A scale developed by Renthlei and Malsawmi (2015), which was used for data collection of data. Likert scale questionnaire was utilizes ranging from 1 to 5.

3.3 Data Analysis

Different statistical tools were used for analysis of the data like one same t-test, Pearson Correlation and Regression. The data were analyzed using SPSS software programs.

4.1 Analysis of Data and Interpretation

4.2 One sample t-test

One sample t-test was used for mean value and mean difference the result is given below table no. 4.2.1.

Table 4.2.1. One sample t-test for teacher attitude toward profession (N=1000)

<i>One-Sample Test</i>									
Test Value = 3									
	M	SD	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Interval Difference	Confidence of the Difference	
							Lower	Upper	
Teacher attitude toward profession	4.28	0.49	36.980	202	.000	1.279	1.21	1.35	

P<0.05

The above results show that majority of the respondent were agree side and the mean value of teacher attitude toward profession was 4.28 which were higher than midpoint 3. The t-value is 36.98 and the mean difference is 1.28 higher than the midpoint 3 value. So p-value is strongly significant at p<0.05.

4.3 Hypothesis no.1

Table 4.3.1. Pearson correlation between teacher attitude toward profession and student academic achievement (N=1000)

		Pearson coefficient (r) with student achievement	
Variables		r	sig
1	Teacher attitude toward profession	0.511	.000
2	Student average score		

The above results show that teachers attitude towards profession was positively contribute towards students' academic achievements. The value r score was 0.511 which was highly significant at p<0.05. So the null hypothesis is rejected.

4.4. Hhypothesis no. 2

Regression analysis was for hypothesis no 2. The model summary and result is given below.

Table 4.4.1. Summary of model (N=1000)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.628 ^a	.394	.385		7.540

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher attitude toward profession and students academic achievement

The above result shows that how the predictors were able to predict students' academic achievement. R is 0.628, R square is 0.394, R square adjusted is .385 and Std. Error of the Estimate is 7.540. The whole estimated model is fit as per the criteria suggesting that the predictors were good with regard to predicting academic achievement of student. So the null hypothesis is rejected.

5.1. Findings

The main finding of the research paper was that majority of teachers observed that teaching profession as an important profession. Mostly teachers appealed that they were punctual and reliable. Some teachers told that they could interconnect efficiently with parents, colleagues and students. It was also was found that the mean value of teacher attitude toward profession was 4.28 so the result showing that majority of teachers had positive attitude toward their profession. The result was found that Pearson correlation (r) for teacher attitude toward profession and student average score was 0.511 which was strongly significant at p<0.05.

5.2. Conclusions

The conclusion of this research paper that majority of teachers had positive attitude toward their profession. It was also concluded that there was a positive relationship between teachers' attitude towards profession and students' academic achievement. It was concluded that the whole research paper was statistically significant.

5.3 Recommendations

Recommendation of the study is that teacher's attitude towards profession was the major predictor of students' academic achievement and it is recommended that teachers should demonstrate positive behavior towards their profession for further development. Training programs (Pre-service & In-service) should focus on improved positive behavior towards their profession.

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